

Physalis grisea (Waterf.) M.Martínez (Solanaceae): A new distributional record for India

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Abstract

The occurrence of *Physalis grisea* (Solanaceae) in India is reported for the first time. Detailed description, a taxonomic comparison and images are provided.

The genus *Physalis* commonly known as husk tomato or ground cheery and it is characterized by inflated fruiting calyces that enclose the fruit. It comprises about 90 species (POWO, 2018) and the centre of diversity is Mexico with over 70 species (Whitson & Manos, 2005), most of which are endemic to South America (Martinez, 1998; Hunziker, 2001). *Physalis* is well known for its edible fruits (Kallianpur et al., 2016; Ganapathy, 1988) but it is an extremely puzzling genus among Solanaceae with considerable taxonomic and nomenclatural complexity (Hepper, 1987; Sudhakaran & Ganapathi, 1993, 1999). Deb (1980) has enumerated six species viz., *P. alkekengi* L., *P. angulata* L., *P. ixocarpa* Brot. ex DC., *P. longifolia* Nutt. and *P. peruviana* L. from India, there after four species viz., *Physalis alvarisii* M.R. Almeida & S.M. Almeida, *P. heterophylla* Nees, *P. joidiasii* M. R.Almeida & S.M. Almeida and *Physalis maxima* Mill. have been added to the *Physalis* of India (Almeida, 2001; Babu, 1977; Raju et al., 2007; Singh & Pandey, 2002). In Tamil Nadu, it is represented by six species (Kottaimuthu & Kalidass, 2015).

During botanical surveys conducted by the first author for the documentation of Solanaceae of Tamil Nadu, the author was stumbled upon by certain *Physalis* specimens collected from the coastal areas of Nagapattinam district. Critical studies with relevant literature (Sullivan, 2004; Waterfall, 1958) and type specimens housed at Gray Herbarium it was authenticated as *Physalis grisea*. On reviewing literature it came to know that hitherto the strawberry tomato has not been reported from India. Thus the present collection constitutes a new distributional record for India. It is described here under with detailed description, phenology and other relevant details for easy identification of the taxa in the field.

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Figure 1. *Physalis grisea*.

a-Habit; **b**-stem; **c** & **d**-leaf abaxial and adaxial view; **e**-flower bud; **f**-flower; **g**-fruits

Taxonomic Treatment

Physalis grisea (Waterf.) M.Martínez in Taxon 42(1): 104. 1993. *Physalis pubescens* Porter & J.M.Coult. var. *grisea* Waterf. in Rhodora 60: 167. 1958. (Figure 1).

Annual, erect herbs, 30-60 cm high; stem angular, much branched, spreading, covered with glandular-pubescent hairs. Leaves simple, alternate; lamina broadly ovate, 4-10 x 3-9.2 cm, hoary green when fresh, drying orange or with orange patches, glandular-pubescent on both surfaces, base rounded-cordate, margin coarsely dentate, acute at apex. Petioles 3-7 cm long. Flowers yellow, solitary, axillary; pedicels 5-6 mm long. Calyx-tube pubescent, lobes 1.5-3 mm long, pubescent. Corolla yellow, campanulate, with 5 large, dark brown spots in the throat; corolla-lobes up to 8 mm long. Stamens 5, epipetalous; anther blue, 1-2 mm long, filaments half as wide as anthers. Ovary ovoid-subglobose, 3-5 mm long. Fruiting calyx green, 5-angled, sunken at base, 2-3.5 cm long, 1.5-2.5 cm in diameter; fruiting pedicel 5-12 mm long.

Flowering & Fruiting: November-January.

Distribution: INDIA (Tamil Nadu), ALABAMA, BELGIUM, ILLIONIS, TENNESSEE, and VERMONT.

Specimens examined: U.S.A., Massachusetts, Cambridge, 24 Sep 1884, Deane *s.n.* (Barcode 00003293GH!); Tamil Nadu, Nagapattinam District, Vedaranyam, around the temple premises, 10° 22' 29 N; 79° 50' 57 E, *R. Kottaimuthu 30118* (TCH!); Velankanni to Vellapallam road side, 10° 41' 08 N; 79° 50' 02 E, *R. Kottaimuthu 30139* (TCH!).

Taxonomic note: *Physalis grisea* is often confused with *P. pruinosa* (Martinez, 1993), but it can be distinguished from the latter by its corolla with brown spots on the throat (vs corolla with 5 pale green inconspicuous spots on the throat), fruiting calyx as long as broad, acute at apex (fruiting calyx longer than broad, acuminate at apex) anthers blue (vs anthers yellow) and leaves dentate from base and drying orange (leaves dentate from middle and drying yellow).

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References

- Almeida, M.R. (2001) *Flora of Maharashtra*, Vol. III. Mumbai, Orient Press.
- Babu, C.R. (1977) *Herbaceous flora of Dehra Dun*. New Delhi, Council of Scientific and Industrial Research.
- Deb, D.B. (1980) Enumeration, synonymy and distribution of the Solanaceae in India. *Journal of Economic and Taxonomic Botany*. 1, 33–54.
- Ganapathy, A. (1988) On the occurrence of *Physalis angulata* L. in Tamil Nadu. *Current Science*. 57(2), 98–99.
- Hepper, F.N. (1987) Solanaceae. In: Dassanayake, M.D. & Fosberg, F.R. (eds.) *A revised handbook to the flora of Ceylon*. Vol. 6. New Delhi, Amerind Publishing Co. Pvt. Ltd.
- Hunziker, A.T. (2001) *Genera Solanacearum. The genera of Solanaceae illustrated, arranged according to a new system*. Ruggell, Gantner Verlag.
- Kallianpur, S.S., Gokarn, R.A. & Rajashekhar, N. (2016) Identity of Ṭāṅkāri (*Physalis minima* Linn.) in Ayurvedic classics: A literature review. *Ancient Science of Life*. 36(1), 216–230.
- Kottaimuthu, R. & Kalidass, C. (2015) *Physalis pruinosa* L. (Solanaceae)-Addition to the flora of Tamil Nadu. *Indian Journal of Forestry*. 38(1), 77–78.
- Martinez, M. (1993) The correct application of *Physalis pruinosa* L. (Solanaceae). *Taxon*. 42, 103–104.
- Martinez, M. (1998) Revisión of *Physalis* section *Epeteiorhiza* (Solanaceae). *Anales del Instituto de Biología serie Botánica*. 69, 71–117.
- POWO (2018) *Physalis*.
<http://powo.science.kew.org/taxon/urn:lsid:ipni.org:names:329952-2#children> (accessed on 14 November 2018).
- Raju, V.S., Reddy, C.S. & Rajarao, K.G. (2007) The myth of minima and maxima, the species of *Physalis* in the Indian subcontinent. *Acta Phytotaxonomic Sinica*. 45(2), 239–245.
- Singh, V. & Pandey, R.P. (2002) *Physalis maxima* Miller - A new record from India. *Indian Journal of Forestry*. 25(1–2), 187–190.
- Sudhakaran, S. & Ganapathi, A. (1993) Structure and distribution of plant trichomes in relation to taxonomy: Indian *Physalis* L. *Feddes Repertorium*. 104(7–8), 469–474.
- Sudhakaran, S. & Ganapathi, A. (1999) Biosystematics of South Indian *Physalis*. In: Nee, M., Symon, D.E., Lester, R.N. & Jessop, J.P. (eds.) *Solanaceae IV: Advances in Biology and Utilization*. Kew, Royal Botanic Gardens, pp. 335–340.
- Sullivan, J. R. (2004) The genus *Physalis* (Solanaceae) in the South eastern United states. *Rhodora*. 106(928), 305–326.

Waterfall, U.T. (1958) A taxonomic study of the genus *Physalis* in North America North of Mexico (concluded). *Rhodora*. 60(714), 152–173.

Whitson, M. & Manos, P.S. (2005) Untangling *Physalis* (Solanaceae) from the Physaloids: a two-gene phylogeny of the Physalinae. *Systematic Botany*. 30, 216–230.